

INCREASE

FROM WASTE TO VALUE

Systemic Pathways to Recycled Plastics
Uptake in the EU Electronics Sector

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ABOUT INCREASE

Plastics recycling is an important lever in the EU's fight against climate change. Despite efforts, most plastics still end up in landfills or being incinerated. The EU-funded INCREASE project seeks to close this gap by applying interdisciplinary solutions across the entire plastics recycling value chain. Its overarching objective is to enable an increased uptake of recycled plastics in added value products such as electrical and electronic equipment, through innovative and systemic solutions spanning every step of the chain, from material design, sorting and recycling technologies to end-use manufacturing. To achieve this, INCREASE brings together partners from across the value chain, combining complementary expertise to address the missing links in plastics recycling and pave the way for wider use of recycled plastic materials.

This white paper is based on the outcomes of the INCREASE project and was prepared by the following partners:

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GLOSSARY

Quality Demands: The technical, regulatory, and functional requirements that recycled materials must meet to substitute virgin plastics in manufactured products.

Quality of Recycling: The extent to which a recycling process preserves material properties so that recyclates can substitute virgin material in specific end-use applications.

Recycling Cascade: A sequential combination of technologies to material recovery and recyclates quality.

Clustering: The strategic pre-sorting of collected waste into groups with similar material compositions to improve sorting efficiency and recyclate consistency.

Waste-push/Demand pull: A policy shift from managing waste outputs toward stimulating demand for high-quality secondary raw materials through market and design incentives.

ABBREVIATIONS

ABBREVIATION	MEANING
ABS	Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene
CE	Circular Economy
CRM	Critical Raw Material
DfR	Design For Recycling
DPP	Digital Product Passport
EEE	Electrical and Electronic Equipment
EoW	End-Of-Waste
EPR	Extended Producer Responsibility
ESD	Electrostatic discharge
ESPR	Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation
LHA	Large Household Appliances
NIR	Near-infrared
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturers
PC	Polycarbonate
Pfi	Plastics for Innovation
PP	Polypropylene
PPWR	Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation
PS	Polystyrene
SRM	Secondary Raw Materials
WEEE	Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment
XRF	X-ray fluorescence

KEY MESSAGES

- 1 A persistent quality gap limits market uptake of recyclates
- 2 Clustering end-of life products significantly improves quality of recyclates
- 3 Clear definitions and harmonised standards are critical market enablers
- 4 Current policy frameworks remain predominantly waste-push oriented
- 5 Circular plastics policy cannot be adjusted in isolation, requiring a coherent policy strategy

INTRODUCTION: MOVING FROM A WASTE-PUSH TO A DEMAND-PULL PERSPECTIVE OF PLASTICS RECYCLING

A Need for Systems Transformation

Plastics contribute to all three dimensions of the planetary crisis – climate change, pollution, and biodiversity loss – requiring a systemic shift toward a circular economy (CE) that engages all sectors and stakeholders across the plastics value chain [1].

An absolute reduction in fossil-based plastic use remains the most effective pathway. While recycling of certain mono-materials, particularly in packaging, has progressed, overall quantity-based recycling targets remain unmet. Consequently, a persistent mismatch remains between the quality of secondary plastics supplied and the quality demanded by the market. This is especially critical for technical and high-performance plastics used in electronics, automotive, textiles, and food-contact applications, where high-quality recyclates are urgently needed [2].

Quality recyclates are also essential for achieving net-zero goals. Although the technical knowledge to produce them exists, science-based and strategic approaches are still lacking to preserve material functionality over time and maintain recyclability across multiple cycles. Current practices often rely on high additive use, which may enable initial recycling but undermines subsequent recyclability. Recyclability should instead be designed from the outset, guided by precise molecular composition and tailored, batch-specific strategies.

Despite progress, the market continues to deliver insufficient volumes of qualitative circular plastics [2]. Stronger policies are needed to accelerate systems transformation: resource mobilisation and infrastructure scaling remain limited, market development is slow, and ongoing disputes over the legitimacy of different recycling pathways hinder progress toward the “take-off” phase. Targeted, directional policymaking is crucial to unlock the transition toward a truly circular plastics system.

From waste-push to demand-pull policies

Designing materials for true circularity requires rethinking how recycling is embedded within broader waste and resource policies. This shift is essential to increase recycled content in products and effectively close plastics material loops.

Over the past decade, EU waste policy has shifted from landfill and incineration toward recycling in line with the waste hierarchy. Early reliance on incineration with energy recovery was replaced by source-separated collection to recover materials and reduce environmental impacts. Policy targets have evolved from cutting landfilling to setting collection and recycling rate goals for specific materials. The Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive, for example, mandates a 50% recycling rate for plastics by 2025. However, weight-based targets for waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) and End-of-Life Vehicles favour heavier materials, disadvantaging plastics.

This approach has led to a persistent gap between the supply of recycled plastics and **manufacturers' quality demands**, particularly where materials must match technical performance of virgin material. Recyclates often fail to meet product specifications, limiting market uptake and slowing progress toward higher recycled content [3].

For the purpose of the INCREASE project, **manufacturers' quality demands** are defined as the combined requirements for purity, uniformity, mechanical and functional performance, regulatory compliance, safety, substitutability with virgin materials, and circularity, with additional criteria such as aesthetics, odour, and cost where relevant [4]. Manufacturers typically benchmark these demands against primary materials and assess secondary materials through iterative testing to verify compliance before market integration.

Quality of recycling is defined as the extent to which recycling preserves the technical properties and functionality of materials so that recyclates can effectively substitute primary raw materials in specific end-use applications [5], [6]. It depends largely on upstream collection, sorting, and treatment processes, which determine the preservation of material value and performance across recycling cycles [7].

The EU's CE concept marks a shift from a waste management ("**waste push**") approach, focused on treating waste after it occurs, to sustainable resource management ("**demand pull**"), which stimulates demand for high-quality secondary materials. This new logic treats society as an "urban mine," integrating material recovery into the broader economy and aligning recycling with industrial demand. It moves the system from managing waste at the end of life to designing value retention from the outset [7], [8].

ENABLING THE DEMAND-PULL PERSPECTIVE; RESTRUCTURING RECYCLING CHAINS

From a demand-side perspective, circular plastics should start from the quality requirements of producers and original equipment manufacturers (OEMs). Meeting these requirements depends on reorganising and supporting collection and sorting systems so they can deliver recyclates that comply with industrial specifications.

Collection and clustering

Assigning waste fractions to the most appropriate recycling routes – mechanical, chemical, and dissolution (as detailed in the next chapter) – supports sustainable resource management and reduces waste. Mechanical recycling is efficient for clean, physically separable streams; chemical recycling can convert more complex, mixed materials; and dissolution recycling enables flexible, high-recovery selective separation of specific types of plastics.

Each stage of the process depends on the efficiency of the preceding steps and on the composition and characteristics of the collected post-consumer waste [9], [10], [11]. Variations in polymer type, colour, and additive content strongly affect the quality of the sorted material. Because most end-of-life plastics products are collected in highly heterogeneous batches, significant variations occur both within and between batches [9], [12]. As a result, sorted output streams often contain high levels of impurities and polymer cross-contamination. Moreover, many recovered plastics are weathered or partially degraded, reducing their processability and mechanical performance [13].

In WEEE treatment, the sequence of operations begins with shredding of the input material. The shredded material is subsequently subjected to magnetic and eddy-current separation to remove ferrous and non-ferrous metals, respectively. Fines are then sieved off, and remaining metals and printed circuit boards (PCBs) are removed from the coarse fraction. The resulting plastic-rich fraction may subsequently undergo additional separation processes, such as density-based sink–float separation, electrostatic separation, or sensor-based sorting (e.g., near-infrared (NIR), FT-Raman, or X-ray fluorescence (XRF)) to recover and classify different polymer types [9], [19], [20], [21].

As highlighted in the INCREASE findings below, clustering end-of-life products by type offers a strategic opportunity to improve recovery across the **recycling cascade**. Studies show that large household appliances (LHA) such as washing machines, dishwashers, and dryers contain high shares of polypropylene (PP), whereas furnaces and air conditioners contain significantly less, indicating strong potential for targeted clustering of PP-rich streams [14], [15]. Small domestic appliances (SDA) generally contain less PP overall, but specific product types such as irons, water heaters, and coffee machines offer notable recovery potential [16], [17], [18]. By grouping

products with similar material compositions, recyclers can streamline sorting, increase purity, reduce contamination, and deliver more consistent feedstocks for mechanical recycling – supporting a more efficient **recycling cascade**.

INCREASE FINDINGS:

QUALITY BENEFITS OF CLUSTERING

Clustering end-of-life copiers improves performance across the **recycling cascade** because their polymer mix is relatively homogeneous, dominated by ABS, PC/ABS, PS and PP). Isolating this stream enables more uniform sorting inputs, reduces cross-contamination, and facilitates dismantling of large parts to remove high-value polymers (e.g., ABS) before shredding. The resulting recyclates show more consistent melt-flow and lower degradation than mixed WEEE, increasing yield, stabilising quality, and enabling higher-value applications.

Recycling cascade

Quantity and quality targets for recycled plastics cannot be achieved through a single recycling technology. Each technology has distinct input requirements and delivers different output qualities. To maximise material recovery and align output quality with market demand, a cascading approach is needed that combines the strengths of mechanical, dissolution, and chemical recycling.

The **recycling cascade** reflects the diversity of advanced recycling technologies, each suited to specific materials and applications. Selecting the appropriate method depends on the material composition, contamination level, and quality requirements of the target product.

Mechanical recycling physically reprocesses materials through shredding, washing, and remelting.

- *Opportunities:* well-established infrastructure; highly efficient for clean, single-polymer streams.
- *Limitations:* Material degradation during reprocessing and limited ability to handle contaminated or mixed plastic waste streams.

Dissolution recycling uses solvents to dissolve target polymers and separate them from contaminants.

- *Opportunities:* effective for complex fractions containing additives or flame retardants; can yield high purity recyclates. polymer chains remain intact.
- *Limitations:* requires careful solvent management and involves higher operational complexity.

Chemical recycling converts polymers into their original monomers or other chemical feedstocks.

- *Opportunities:* can treat mixed or contaminated waste streams and produce virgin-grade materials, including food-contact use.
- *Limitations:* higher costs and energy demand compared to other recycling methods.

A cascading integration of these technologies enables optimal use of each method's strengths – mechanical recycling as the primary route, supported by dissolution and chemical processes for complex fractions. This holistic approach increases recovery rates, improves recyclates quality, and reduces material losses, contributing to a more resilient and efficient circular plastics system.

EXAMPLE OF A RECYCLING CASCADE

Conducting trials of the recycling cascade with LHA as input source show that integrating mechanical, dissolution, and chemical recycling improves yield and recycles quality. Mechanical recycling recovers clean, unfilled PP; dissolution recycling treats additive- and filler-rich parts (e.g., flame-retarded fractions) to recover polymers such as ABS or filled PP; and chemical recycling, for instance pyrolysis, converts residual mixed/contaminated streams from different sources into virgin-grade feedstocks (e.g., naphtha). Together, the **recycling cascade** maximises energy recovery, increases high-quality secondary supply, reduces fossil dependence, and strengthens system efficiency and resilience.

ENABLING A MARKET FOR RECYCLED CONTENT: CLARIFYING KEY TERMINOLOGY

While advancing recycling technologies is essential, their impact will remain limited without parallel efforts to establish markets, harmonise definitions, and implement policies that drive demand for high-quality secondary materials. Clarifying key terminology is thus crucial.

What are recycled plastics?

A lack of clear and consistent definitions remains a major barrier to standardisation and effective policymaking in plastics recycling. Ambiguous terminology and differing national regulations create uncertainty for producers seeking to replace virgin materials with recyclates. Harmonised standards and definitions are therefore essential to increase trust, transparency, and comparability of recycled content claims.

Although “recyclate” is defined in several international standards, such as ISO 472:2013, CEN/TR 15353:2007, and DIN SPEC 91446, these definitions are interpreted broadly and often overlap with terms like “secondary raw material,” “recycled plastics,” or “regenerate.” As a result, the concept lacks uniform understanding, leading to inconsistent claims and regulatory misalignment across markets.

TERM	DEFINITION / CONTEXT	SOURCE / NOTES
Recycled Plastic	Plastic resulting from the decontamination stage of a recycling process and subsequent post-processing operations, not yet transformed into recycled plastic materials and articles.	Based on Food Contact Regulation (EU) 2022/1616
Recycled Plastic Materials and Articles	“[Target application e.g. food contact] materials and articles in their finished state, made either fully or partly of recycled plastic.”	Suggested adaptation for general use, based on Food Contact Regulation (EU) 2022/1616
Recyclate	The terms “secondary raw material,” “recycled plastics,” and “regenerate” are often used synonymously with “recyclates.” However, inconsistent use has led to ambiguity, limiting its regulatory and technical precision.	Various standards and technical documents

INCREASE FINDINGS:

The INCREASE project did not adopt ISO 472:2013's definition of "recyclates" because it lacks practical specificity. It allows materials to be labelled "recycled" after decontamination and reprocessing, even if they never become usable products; in practice, some recyclers process and screen materials only to incinerate low-quality outputs, often supported by public funding rather than market demand.

Unlike definitions for "recycled plastics" or "recycled plastic materials and articles," ISO 472 does not specify key parameters – material type, quality level, or recycling process – needed for standardisation, market transparency, and product development. INCREASE therefore recommends that future definitions of "recyclates" explicitly reference material characteristics, achieved quality grade, and the recycling process applied. To support a harmonised framework for defining recycled content, the team reviewed European standards, scientific literature, and grey publications from public and private sources, screened and compared relevant terms to identify overlaps and inconsistencies, and then assessed candidate definitions against the INCREASE recycling routes (mechanical, dissolution, chemical) for selection at each process step.

Output (Material) = "Input (Material) + (Recycling) Process"

For example, ISO 472:2013 defines recycled plastics as:

Recycled Plastic: "Plastic prepared by processing in a production process from plastic waste materials for the original purpose or for other purposes but excluding energy recovery."

Both input and output may refer to materials or waste items that have not yet been processed to the material level (e.g., unshredded products). Based on this logic, the following definitions, drawn from existing standards and regulations, are considered most relevant for the INCREASE framework.

Calculating recycled content

The calculation of recycled content depends strongly on the point in the production process at which the recycled material is declared as 100%.

Non-harmonised rules illustrate how differing calculation boundaries can lead to significant discrepancies in reported recycled content. Without clear and harmonised criteria, several risks emerge:

Internal (EU) risks:

- Risk of misleading claims and consumer deception due to inconsistent calculation methods.
- Competitive disadvantages for companies adhering to stricter standards.
- Compliance challenges arising from divergent national interpretations.

External (trade) risks:

- Products imported from regions with less stringent definitions may undermine EU recycling quality goals.
- Threats to recyclers and manufacturers dependent on high-quality recyclates if markets are flooded with falsely labelled products.

Mass balance allocation methods, where recycled content is averaged across a production system rather than physically traced, further complicate the measurement of recycled content. Depending on how mass balance is applied:

- The actual recycled content in specific products may be overstated.
- Incentives to use high-quality recyclates can be weakened.
- Trust in recycling claims and labelling may erode.

Different chain of custody models, such as segregated, controlled blending, and book-and-claim, also determine how transparently recycled content is tracked along the value chain. Clear and harmonised rules for these accounting approaches are essential to ensure credibility, comparability, and consumer trust in recycled content claims.

Example of a calculation with regards to a specific EEE device

For example, 50 grams of recycled plastics are compounded with 100 grams of virgin plastic, fillers, and additives to produce 150 grams of intermediate material, representing 33.3% recycled content. This compound is then used to manufacture a 350-gram product. If the original 50 grams of recycled material are traced through to the final product, the resulting recycled content amounts to 14.2%. However, if the compound itself is treated as the new 100% input, the recycled content becomes 42.8%, reflecting the 33.3% recycled share in the compound.

Example of a calculation of “recycled content”

$$\text{Recycled content in the product} = \left(\frac{\text{mass of recycled material in the product}}{\text{total mass of the product}} \right) \times 100\%$$

What is recyclability?

Recyclability is central to the EU circular economy agenda but is defined inconsistently across frameworks. It generally describes whether a material or product can be collected, sorted, and reprocessed into secondary raw materials (SRM) that substitute virgin resources without loss of essential performance, and depends on both material properties and enabling conditions (collection, sorting technology, and stable end-market demand). Recyclability determines whether products remain in productive use or become waste: high recyclability retains value, reduces virgin material dependence and environmental impacts, and supports resilient secondary markets; low recyclability increases waste and undermines the viability of the recycling system. A performance-based framework co-developed with industry is essential to balance ambition with feasibility and safeguard innovation and competitiveness [19], [20], [21].

Under the Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR), the EU seeks to harmonise recyclability through forthcoming Design for Recycling (DfR) criteria that embed recyclability from the design stage. While aligned with Green Deal and CE goals, uniform rules across diverse packaging functions risk unintended consequences, especially for technically functional tertiary packaging such as electrostatic discharge (ESD) pallets made from WEEE-derived plastics.

Material quality must be defined as fit for purpose: high-purity polymers are essential for sensitive uses, but industrial logistics and electronics transport prioritise durability and electrical performance, which mechanically recycled plastics with additives or fillers can deliver efficiently. Proposed PPWR recyclability performance grades and potential additive restrictions (e.g., carbon black) could nevertheless exclude such functional packaging, diverting valuable streams to incineration and undermining circularity. As DfR criteria and standards remain under development, regulatory differentiation is essential: rules should distinguish packaging types and allow adapted thresholds or exemptions for technically functional products, supported by fit-for-purpose standards that value performance and circularity over universal purity metrics.

WAY FORWARD FOR POLICYMAKERS – FOUR POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

Demand side approach

Current EU policy on plastics and electronics addresses important aspects, such as environmentally sound waste management and product safety, yet very few instruments address a critical gap: stimulating demand for SRM. These demand-side measures are needed to create a level playing field with fossil virgin alternatives and enable the effective reintegration of recovered materials into production systems.

Recent EU initiatives, including the Ecodesign for Sustainability Regulation and the Circular Economy Act, signal a necessary shift toward demand-side policies for recovered materials. However, the timing and design of these measures are critical.

We recommend three immediate priorities for EU policymakers: First, establish a mandatory, standardised calculation method for recycled content. Without this foundation, buyers and suppliers of recycled plastics operate without a level playing field, creating uncertainty and hindering market development. Second, set recycled content targets carefully. Targets that outpace the availability of high-quality

recyclates risk driving up prices and creating cost premiums that ultimately burden consumers and undermine policy acceptance. Third, complement targets with economic measures that level the playing field between recycled and virgin plastics. This includes both incentives for using recycled materials, such as tax breaks or procurement preferences, and disincentives to virgin plastic use, such as levies on virgin materials. Such mechanisms can help bridge the cost gap that often favours virgin materials despite their higher environmental impact.

Creating robust demand for recycled WEEE plastics requires the EU to:

1. Standardising recycled content calculation – Establishing mandatory methods to ensure market transparency
2. Setting realistic recycled content targets – Matching ambition with recyclates availability to avoid market disruption
3. Deploying economic instruments – Using incentives for recycled materials and levies on virgin plastics to bridge cost gaps

End-Of-Waste criteria

Under the EU Waste Framework Directive (2008/98/EC), Articles 5 and 6 define when materials qualify as by-products or reach end-of-waste (EoW) status. Although both Member States and the European Commission can set EoW criteria, implementation remains uneven, creating a fragmented internal market in which divergent national definitions raise trade barriers, increase compliance complexity for recyclers, and deter investment.

EU-wide EoW criteria exist for metals and glass, while criteria for plastics, textiles, and construction waste are still under development. Draft plastics criteria largely focus on mechanical recycling and processes that preserve polymer structure, leaving chemical recycling in a grey area. Because chemical recycling breaks polymers down into monomers or hydrocarbons that can be used for both material and fuel applications, EoW rules must clearly define which outputs qualify as recyclates to ensure these routes deliver genuine material recovery. EoW classification also directly affects cross-border shipments: materials treated as “waste” face stricter transport controls, and divergent national criteria further hinder circular trade flows within the EU.

To enable a functioning internal market for recyclates, the EU must:

1. Adopt EU-wide EoW criteria for plastics
2. Define clear EoW status for chemical recycling outputs
3. Facilitate cross-border trade of materials meeting EoW standards

Threshold values for hazardous substances

Stricter EU threshold limits for hazardous substances can constrain both the quantity and quality of recycled plastics. While chemical legislation, such as the POP (Persistent Organic Pollutants Regulation), REACH (Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation, and Restriction of Chemicals), and the RoHS Directive (Restriction of Hazardous Substances) are essential for protecting human health and the environment, they also increase compliance burdens for recyclers, who must continuously test outputs to demonstrate that contaminant levels remain below legal limits.

Two recent shifts highlight this tension: (1) lower thresholds for substances such as Polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDEs) under the POP Regulation improve safety but raise testing costs and complexity (e.g. larger sample sizes and specialised laboratory analysis); and (2) moving from single-substance controls to restrictions on entire substance families broadens compliance scope and adds operational and financial pressure. Balancing chemical safety with circularity will require regulation that remains ambitious but feasible, supported by controlled transition measures to enable adaptation without stalling innovation and scale-up .

The EU should adopt a more integrated approach across waste, chemicals, and product legislation by:

1. Strengthening hazardous-substance traceability (e.g., via the Digital Product Passport (DPP));
2. Reducing the use of hazardous substances at the design stage (e.g., eco-design requirements for EEE);
3. Incentivising DfR by linking extended producer responsibility (EPR) fees to product recyclability;
4. Adjusting EPR schemes to better cover the costs of removing hazardous materials during WEEE treatment and recycling

Barriers to accessing finance

The European Union offers a broad range of public and blended funding instruments to support innovation and infrastructure in the CE. While this framework provides a strong foundation for advancing circular plastics, stakeholders and technology developers however report structural barriers to accessing finance for recycled plastics projects, as shown by the INCREASE project. Most EU programmes prioritised early-stage research and development, while projects focused on market uptake, scaling, or infrastructure investment face significant challenges in securing follow-up funding. This situation is further reinforced by a noticeable shift in recent EU work programmes away from plastics towards other priority areas such as Critical Raw Materials (CRMs). This gap is particularly critical for recyclers, who often depend on

decentralised or specialised solutions to consistently meet regulatory and customer quality requirements.

High capital costs, limited risk-sharing mechanisms, and uncertain return on investment further discourage private funding. As a result, there is a misalignment between what the sector needs to reach the next stage and the public and private funds that are available. Leaving many innovative recycling technologies to remain trapped at pilot or demonstration scale, slowing progress toward industrial deployment and system-wide circularity.

A funding environment that enables investments in plastics recycling technologies should be established through:

1. rebalancing the focus of EU-funding instruments toward deployment and scale-up to ensure plastics recycling projects can receive financial support for going beyond pilot and demonstration
2. establishing tailored blended finance and risk-sharing mechanisms that account for the risks concerning capital intensity and uncertainties in return on investment
3. strengthening market conditions and feedstock security to predictable demand for recycled plastics to further derisk investments for recyclers and technology providers

CONCLUSION

While there has been important progress in advancing plastics recycling in the electronics sector, a structural quality gap continues to limit the market uptake of recyclates. Weight-based targets and end-of-life-oriented policies are insufficient to deliver high-quality secondary raw materials that can substitute virgin plastics in demanding applications. A systemic shift in policymaking is therefore essential.

Improving the quality begins upstream already. Clustering end-of-life products, reorganising collection systems, and implementing a cascading integration of mechanical, dissolution, and chemical recycling can significantly increase both yield and functionality. At the same time, clear definitions, harmonised calculation methods, and credible traceability rules are critical to building trust, ensuring fair competition, and preventing misleading recycled-content claims.

Policy coherence is equally crucial. Requirements and rules must be aligned, coherent and standardised to avoid conflicting incentives, hence organised more systematically. Furthermore, barriers to accessing finance, particularly for scale-up and infrastructure, must be addressed to move promising technologies beyond the pilot stage.

In conclusion, circular plastics policy cannot be adjusted in isolation. Only a coordinated, value-chain-oriented strategy, linking design, collection, recycling technologies, market incentives, and consumer engagement, can preserve material functionality while ensuring environmental protection. Delivering high-quality recycled plastics at scale will depend on regulatory clarity, economic alignment, and systemic integration across the European electronic sector and the plastics ecosystem.

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